

Notes on Contributors

Fee-Alexandra Haase:

- Ph. D., Professor, University of Nizwa, Oman;
- author of significant scientific and didactic publications;
- participant in national and international scientific conferences.

Yuliya Gurmak:

- Ph. D. Student, Ivan Franko National University of Lviv, Ukraine;
- author of scientific and didactic publications;
- participant in national and international scientific conferences.

Ioana Boghian:

- Associate Professor, Ph.D., Vasile Alecsandri University of Bacău, Romania;
- author of significant scientific and didactic publications;
- participant in national and international scientific conferences;
- (founder) member of many scientific research teams and societies from Romania and abroad;
- research areas: English philology, Cultural studies, Literary Science, Literary Semiotics.

Olesea Bodean-Vozian:

- Lecturer, MA, Ph. D. Student, Moldova State University;
- interdisciplinary studies in Foreign Languages and Literatures and Law, Moldova State University;
- co-author of "The Consecutive Translator's Handbook", Chisinau, 2011, 164 p.;
- project co-researcher in the EU FP6 "Dimensions of Linguistic Otherness: Prospects of Maintenance and Revitalization of Minority Languages within the New Europe" Project (2006-2008);
- trainer for the School of Professional Translator, ATP (since 2010);
- member of the Association of Professional Translators from Moldova (since 2007);
- member of the Union of Sworn Translators of Moldova (since 2010);
- research interests: cognitive linguistics, translation studies, and minority languages.

Micaela Țaulean:

- Senior Lecturer, Ph.D., Alecu Russo State University of Bălți, Republic of Moldova;
 - participant in national and international scientific conferences;
 - author of scientific and didactic works.
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Bun de tipar 27.05.2015. Garnitura Book Antigua. Comanda nr. 175. Tiraj 50.
Tipografia Universității de Stat „Alec Russo” din Bălți. Mun. Bălți, str. Pușkin, 38.